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Research Article

**RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION
FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF TRAMADOL
HYDROCHLORIDE AND DICLOFENAC IN BULK DRUGS
AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS**¹ Shaik. Reshma, ² Shaik. Althaf, ³ M. Siva prasad.¹⁻³ Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Chalapathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
LAM (v), Tadikonda (M), Guntur district-522034, A.P, India.**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

The aim of the present work was to develop and validate a simple, efficient, economical method for the analysis of Tramadol and Diclofenac in pharmaceutical dosage forms by Rp-HPLC. A hypersil C₁₈ reverse phase column (4.6 × 200, 5 μm) with mobile phase containing 10mm phosphate buffer (pH-4.5): Acetonitrile(30:70v/v) is used and eluents monitored at 270nm. The Retention time of Tramadol and Diclofenac was 2.34 and 4.57 respectively.

The validated characteristics, included, specificity, Linearity, LOD, LOQ, Precision, Accuracy, Robustness, Validation acceptance criteria were met in all cases. The percent recoveries ranged between 95% and 105%. The RSD was found to be less than 2. The method could be successfully used for the analysis of Tramadol and Diclofenac in bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Key Words: Rp-HPLC, Method development, Tramadol, Diclofenac, Validation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Tramadol Hydrochloride is chemically (1R,2R)-2-[(dimethyl amino) methyl]-1-(3-methoxyphenyl) cyclohexanol hydrochloride (Fig 1). Tramadol belongs to analgesic and narcotic category. Tramadol and its O-desmethyl metabolite (M1) are selective, weak OP3-receptor agonists. It is indicated in the treatment of moderate to severe pain. Tramadol is used to treat postoperative, dental, cancer, and acute musculoskeletal pain and as an adjuvant to NSAID therapy in patients with osteoarthritis.

Diclofenac sodium is chemically Sodium 2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl) amino] phenyl acetate (Figure 2). It is used as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agent and is official in BP, USP. It acts by the inhibition of leukocyte migration and the enzyme cyclooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2), leading to the peripheral inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis. Diclofenac is used in acute and chronic treatment of signs and symptoms of osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. Diclofenac is also available in topical forms and has been found to be useful for osteoarthritis but not other types of long-term musculoskeletal pain. It may also help with actinic keratosis, and acute pain caused by minor strains, sprains, and contusions (bruises).

The developed method is validated method for the Analysis of Tramadol Hydrochloride and Diclofenac Sodium in bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage forms which is Precise, accurate, Simple and Economical

Fig:1 Tramadol

Diclofenac

Fig:2

Table:1 Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Column	Hypersil C18 (4.6 × 200,5µm)
Buffer	13.8 grams of Pottassium dihydrogen ortho Phosphate in 1000 mL water; pH 4.5 was adjusted with Orthophosphoric acid.
Mobile phase	Acetonitrile and Phosphate Buffer(70:30v/v)
Flow Rate	1.2ml/min
Wave length	270nm
Injection Volume	20µl
Run time	10 min

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals: Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer, Tramadol, Diclofenac, HPLC water.

Equipment: High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC)

Preparation of Reagents and Standards-**Preparation of 10mm phosphate buffer solution (Ph 4.5)**

13.8grams of potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 1000ml HPLC grade water and Ph was adjusted to 4.5 with phosphoric acid. Then it is filtered through vacuum filtration and it was degassed in ultrasonicator.

Preparation of mobile phase

The prepared buffer and Acetonitrile were mixed in the Ratio of 70:30v/v and was filtered through.

Preparation of standard stock solutions

Accurately weighed amount of 100mg of Tramadol Hydrochloride & 100 mg of Diclofenac Sodium were taken to a 100 mL cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was then diluted with 70mL of mobile phase and sonicated. The volume was made to 100 mL with the same solvent. This was marked and labeled as Stock solution.

Preparation of sample solution (dosage form):

Take 20 Dibal tablet & weigh them. Crush the contents into powder form. Calculate a weight equivalent to 100mg of Diclofenac Sodium & 100 mg of Tramadol Hydrochloride & take into a 100mL volumetric flask. Add 50mL of Mobile Phase & sonicate for 10min. Filter under vacuum filtration unit & makeup the volume. From this 0.4mL was pipetted into a 10mL volumetric flask & make up with mobile phase such that the final concentrations are 40µg/mL of Diclofenac Sodium & 60 µg/mL of Tramadol Hydrochloride.

Selection of detector and wave length:

The spectra of various diluted standard solution Tramadol and Diclofenac in mobile phase were recorded using PDA detector. The peak of maximum absorbance was observed at 270nm.

Validation of the proposed method:

The proposed method was validated according to the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. Validation is an integral part of analytical method development. Once the method has been developed, it is necessary to evaluate under the conditions expected for real samples before being used for a specific purpose. The following parameters were evaluated. They are- System Suitability, Linearity, Accuracy, Limit of detection, Limit of Quantification, Robustness

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Analytical method validation**

1.System suitability: System suitability test should be carried out to verify that the analytical system is working properly and can give accurate and precise results. Standard solutions were prepared as per the test method and injected into the chromatographic system. The system suitability parameters were evaluated from resolution, retention times and theoretical plates of standard chromatograms. The % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Table: 2 System suitability parameters for Tramadol and diclofenac.

S.No.	System Suitability Parameters	Results	
		Tramadol	Diclofenac
1	Tailing factor(T_f)	1.3	1.0
2	Resolution (Rs)	-	9.086
3	Retention time(Rt)	2.434	4.573
4	Theoretical plates(N)	18187	27559

2.Linearity: The linearity of an analytical method was carried out to check its ability to elicit test results that are directly, or by a well-defined mathematical transformation, proportional to the concentration of analyte in samples within a given range. Different levels of standard solutions were Prepared and inject into the HPLC and the chromatograms were recorded.

Acceptance criteria : Correlation coefficient should not be less than 0.996.

Table: 3 Linearity table for Tramadol and diclofenac

S.no	Tramadol		Diclofenac	
	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak area	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak area
1	5	120338	5	73588
2	10	252875	10	136430
3	15	381096	15	207739
4	20	524066	20	271807
5	25	630671	25	351568
	$R^2 = 0.998$		$R^2 = 0.999$	

Fig :3 Calibration curve of Tramadol

Fig:4 Calibration curve of diclofenac

Discussion: Five linear concentrations of Tramadol (5-25µg/ml) and diclofenac (5-25µg/ml) were injected in a triplicate manner. Average areas were mentioned above and linearity equations obtained for Tramadol was $y = 25837x + 5747.9$ and diclofenac was $y = 40044x + 5747.9$. Correlation coefficients obtained for Tramadol 0.998 and diclofenac 0.999.

Fig:5 Linearity Chromatogram

Table :4 Linearity chromatogram

Name		Retention time	Area	Tailing factor	Theoretical plates/meter
Tramadol	Chromatogram1	2.434	120338	1.341	18187
	Chromatogram2	2.438	252875	1.104	20738
	Chromatogram3	2.489	381096	1.132	19480
	Chromatogram4	2.489	524066	1.132	19480
	Chromatogram5	2.492	630671	1.174	28712
Diclofenac	Chromatogram1	4.573	73588	1.077	27559
	Chromatogram2	4.572	136430	1.035	29967
	Chromatogram3	4.644	207739	1.049	28912
	Chromatogram4	4.644	271807	9.242	28912
	Chromatogram5	4.562	351568	1.041	28304

3.Precision:

The precision of an analytical method is a measure of the random error and is defined as the agreement between replicate measurements of the same sample. It is expressed as the percentage coefficient of variation (%CV) or relative standard deviation (RSD) of the replicate measurements.

$$\% \text{RSD} = \frac{\text{standard deviation}}{\text{mean}} \times 100$$

(a)System Precision:

For precision studies 6 replicate injections of Tramadol and diclofenac standard were performed. % RSD was determined for peak areas of Tramadol and diclofenac.

Table: 5 System precision table of Tramadol and diclofenac.

S.no	Tramadol	Diclofenac
1	252874	136430
2	254896	136297
3	256198	135590
4	259102	139323
5	257310	137342
6	253489	136926
Mean	255644.83	136484.7
S.D	2362.90	1290.315
%RSD	0.9242	0.9419

Fig.6 System precision chromatogram injection

Discussion: six injections was given and the obtained areas were mentioned above. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for three drugs and obtained as 0.9242% and 1.1298% respectively for Tramadol and diclofenac. As the limit of Precision was less than “2” the system precision was passed in this method.

(B) Intra-day:

Repeatability expresses the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time. Repeatability is also termed as Intra-assay precision.

Table :6 Intra-day table of Tramadol and diclofenac.

S.no	Tramadol	Diclofenac
Mean	254333.16	138257.16
S.D	2539.19	1423.89
%RSD	0.9983	1.0298

Fig.7 Intra-day chromatogram injection-**(c) Intermediate precision (Day_ Day Precision):**

Intermediate precision of the analytical method was determined by performing method precision on another day by different analysts under same experimental condition. Assay of all five replicate sample preparations was determined and mean % assay value, standard deviation & % RSD was calculated.

Acceptance criteria

The % RSD for the area of five standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Table :7 Intermediate precision table of Tramadol and Diclofenac

S.no	Tramadol	DICLOFENAC
Mean	252446.2	136657.3
S.D	2984.907	1416.703
%RSD	1.182	1.036

Fig.8 Intermediate precision chromatogram injection**Table:8 Accuracy Table**

Peak no	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Tailing Factor	Resolution	Theoretical plates/ meter (USP)
1	Tramadol	2.434	252875	1.341	-----	18187
2	Diclofenac	4.573	136372	1.077	9.086	27559
Total			389247			

Discussion: As the limit of Precision was less than “2” the system precision was passed in this method

4.Accuracy:

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value found

Acceptance Criteria: The % Recovery for each level should be between 95.0 to 105.

Table :9 Accuracy table of Tramadol

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area			Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
	Sample Area	Average	Standard Area				
50 %	126437	121460	252875	5.00	4.86	97.2	98.75
	125783						
	127345						
100 %	252875	253585	252875	10.0	10.02	100.2	98.75
	254851						
	253029						
150 %	379312	375101	252875	15.0	14.83	98.86	98.75
	373920						
	372073						

Table :10 Accuracy table of diclofenac.

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area			Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
	Sample Area	Average	Standard Area				
50 %	68215	67962	136430	5.0	4.98	99.6	97.93
	68291						
	67381						
100 %	136430	136668	136430	10.0	9.56	95.6	97.93
	138371						
	135204						
150 %	204645	200583	136430	15.0	14.79	98.6	97.93
	208732						
	206384						

Fig 9: Accuracy 50% chromatogram

Fig 7.13 Accuracy 100% chromatogram

Fig 10: Accuracy 150% chromatogram Sensitivity:

5.LOD sample Preparation:

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantities. The detection limit can be calculated based on the Standard Deviation of the Response and the Slope.

The parameter LOD was determined on the basis of response and slope of the regression equation. The Detection Limit (DL) may be expressed as:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \text{ F/S}$$

F = Residual Standard deviation of the response,

S = Slope of the calibration curve.

The LOD for this method was found to be 1.57 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Tramadol, 1.60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for diclofenac respectively.

6.LOQ sample Preparation: The parameter LOQ was determined on the basis of response and slope of the regression equation. The Quantization Limit (QL) may be expressed as:

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \text{ F/S}$$

Where, F = Residual Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve.

The LOQ for this method was found to be 4.73 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Tramadol, 4.82 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for diclofenac respectively.

Table :11 sensitivity table of Tramadol and diclofenac sodium

	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Tramadol	4.73	1.57
Diclofenac	4.82	1.60

7.Robustness: The robustness of an analytical method is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage. Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate, mobile phase ratio, and wavelength are made but there were no recognized change in the result and are within range as per ICH Guide lines.

Robustness conditions like Flow minus (1ml/min), Flow plus (1.5ml/min), mobile phase minus (55:45), mobile phase plus (80:20), Wavelength minus (230) and Wavelength plus (300) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed and all are within the limit.

Table:12 Robustness data for Tramadol

S.No	Parameter	Tramadol		
		RT (min)	Theoretical plate count	Resolution
1	Standard	2.434	18187	0.00000
2	Change in organic phase ratio(-)55:45	2.457	19480	0.00000
3	Change in organic phase ratio(+)80:20	2.493	19345	0.00000
4	Change in flow rate(-) 1.0ml/ min	2.447	19632	0.00000
5	Change in flow rate(+)1.5ml/ min	2.404	18261	0.00000
6	Change in wavelength (-)230	2.469	19482	0.00000
7	Change in wave length (+)300	2.453	18463	0.00000

Table 13 Robustness data for diclofenac

S.No	Parameter	Diclofenac		
		RT (min)	Theoretical plate count	Resolution
1	Standard	4.573	27559	9.242
2	Change in organic phase ratio(-)55:45	4.780	29376	9.086
3	Change in organic phase ratio(+)80:20	4.457	27934	9.063
4	Change in flow rate(-) 1.0ml/ min	4.895	27543	9.349
5	Change in flow rate(+)1.5ml/ min	4.452	28912	9.284
6	Change in wavelength (-)230	4.593	28954	9.371
7	Change in wavelength (+)300	4.745	28952	9.283

ASSAY: The commercial marketed formulation containing 150 mg of Tramadol and 100 mg diclofenac. The sample solution was treated same as standard solution. The solutions were injected into HPLC.

$$\text{Percent Assay} = \frac{\text{Practical Yield}}{\text{Theoretical Yield}} \times 100$$

$$C_{\text{test}} = \frac{\text{area test}}{\text{area standard}} \times 100$$

Table :14 Assay for Tramadol And Diclofenac

Tablet Sample	Label Claim (mg)	Amount Present	Assay%
TRAMADOL	150	148	98.66%
DICLOFENAC	100	98	98.00%

CONCLUSION:

Validation is an integral part of analytical method development. Once the method has been developed, it is necessary to evaluate under the conditions expected for real samples before being used for a specific purpose. After several trials with various solvents, mobile phase system composed of acetonitrile and phosphate buffer was adjusted to 4.5 in the proportion of 70:30 respectively was selected for the simultaneous estimation of Tramadol and diclofenac in combined dosage form by RP-HPLC. wavelength is 270 nm. Mobile phase with the flow rate of 1.2 ml/min gave optimum separation with good resolution between the peaks. A reverse phase C₁₈ column was used as stationary phase. The retention time of Tramadol and diclofenac were found to be 2.434 and 4.573 minutes, respectively. This method is simple, specific and economical.

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